

Supplementary Material for “AI-Lite: Adaptive Data Center Cooling Optimization Based on Machine Learning”

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1 Theoretical Results

In this section, we present a comprehensive analysis of the theoretical performance of AI-Lite. We show that the selection algorithm quickly converges to an optimal solution under some mild conditions.

Theorem 1. *Let $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathcal{R}^d$ and $\delta \in (0, 1)$, with high probability, the regret achieved by AI-Lite is sublinear with respect to T . Precisely,*

$$\Pr \left\{ \text{Reg}_T \leq \mathcal{O} \left(\sqrt{\log(|\mathcal{X}|^{\frac{1}{3}} \pi^{\frac{2}{3}} T / \delta^{\frac{1}{3}})} \cdot \gamma_T \cdot T \right) \right\} \geq 1 - \delta, \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma_T = \mathcal{O}((T \log T)^{\frac{d}{1+d}})$.

1.1 Basic Assumptions

When proving Theorem 1, we need to make the following assumptions.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} y_t = f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t) + \epsilon_t, \quad \epsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2), \\ f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t) = f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t^*) + \text{Err}_t, \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \text{Err}_t \cdot t^\alpha = C, \alpha > 1. \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

The first assumption states that each observation deviates from the true reward due to Gaussian noise with zero mean. The second assumption states that the prediction error caused by the XGBoost regression model asymptotically vanishes at a rate of $1/t^\alpha$, where C is a constant. As the regression model accumulates more training samples over time, this is indeed reasonable, a point we substantiate in Section 2.

1.2 Theoretical Analysis

Before delving into the details of the proof, we first introduce the following lemmas.

Lemma 1. *If $x \sim N(0, 1)$ is drawn from a Gaussian distribution, the upper bound of $\Pr\{x \geq c\}$ is given by:*

$$\Pr\{x \geq c\} \leq \frac{1}{2}e^{-c^2/2}. \quad (3)$$

Proof. The conclusion of this lemma comes from [1].

Lemma 2. *Given $\delta \in (0, 1)$, the following holds with probability at least $1 - \delta$:*

$$\begin{aligned} |f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}_t^*) - \mu_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x})| &\leq \beta_{t,x}\sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}), \\ \text{for all } \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}, t &\geq 1, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\beta_{t,x} = \sqrt{2 \log \left(\frac{|\mathcal{X}|\pi^2 t^3}{6\delta n_{t,x}} \right)}$.

Proof. Since $f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}_t^*)$ is drawn from a Gaussian distribution $N(\mu_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}), \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}))$, by applying Lemma 1, we have:

$$\Pr \left\{ \left| \frac{f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}_t^*) - \mu_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x})}{\sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x})} \right| \geq \beta_{t,x} \right\} \leq \exp \left(-\frac{\beta_{t,x}^2}{2} \right). \quad (5)$$

Given that

$$\exp \left(-\frac{\beta_{t,x}^2}{2} \right) = \frac{6\delta n_{t,x}}{|\mathcal{X}|\pi^2 t^3} \leq \frac{6\delta}{|\mathcal{X}|\pi^2 t^2}, \quad (6)$$

we can refine the expression in (5) as follows:

$$\Pr \left\{ \left| \frac{f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}_t^*) - \mu_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x})}{\sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x})} \right| \geq \beta_{t,x} \right\} \leq \frac{6\delta}{|\mathcal{X}|\pi^2 t^2}. \quad (7)$$

the last inequality stems from $n_{t,x} \leq t$. To complete the proof of this lemma, we leverage the identity $\sum \frac{1}{t^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$ and employ the union bound for $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$, considering the condition $t \geq 1$.

Lemma 3. *For $t \geq 1$, if $|f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}_t^*) - \mu_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x})| \leq \beta_{t,x}\sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x})$ for all $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$, then the regret r_t is upper bounded by $2\beta_{t,x}\sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$.*

Proof. Based on the definition of \mathbf{x}_t , we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\mu_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + \beta_{t,x}\sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \\ &\geq \mu_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*) + \beta_{t,x}\sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*) \\ &\geq f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*, \mathbf{z}_t^*), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

which implies that

$$\begin{aligned}
r_t &= f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*, \mathbf{z}_t^*) - f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t^*) \\
&\leq \mu_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + \beta_{t,x} \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) - f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t^*) \\
&\leq 2\beta_{t,x} \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t).
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 3.

Lemma 4. *The information gain for the points selected can be expressed in terms of the predictive variances. If $\mathbf{f}_T = \{f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)\} \in \mathbb{R}^T$, then*

$$I(\mathbf{y}_T; \mathbf{f}_T) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \log(1 + \sigma^{-2} \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)). \tag{10}$$

Proof. The conclusion of this lemma comes from [3].

Proof (Next, we will prove Theorem 1). First of all, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
(\text{Reg}_T)^2 &= \left\{ \sum_{t=1}^T [f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*, \mathbf{z}_t^*) - f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t)] \right\}^2 \\
&\leq T \sum_{t=1}^T [f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t) - f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*, \mathbf{z}_t^*)]^2 \\
&= T \sum_{t=1}^T [f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t^*) + \text{Err}_t - f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*, \mathbf{z}_t^*)]^2 \\
&= T \sum_{t=1}^T \left\{ [f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t^*) - f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*, \mathbf{z}_t^*)]^2 + \right. \\
&\quad \left. 2\text{Err}_t [f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t^*) - f(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t^*, \mathbf{z}_t^*)] + \text{Err}_t^2 \right\} \\
&\leq T \sum_{t=1}^T \left\{ 4\beta_{t,x}^2 \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + 4\text{Err}_t [\beta_{t,x} \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)] + \text{Err}_t^2 \right\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

The last inequality above is a result of applying Lemma 2 and Lemma 3, specifically, $r_t \leq 2\beta_{t,x} \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$ holds with a probability greater than or equal to $(1 - \delta)$. Introducing the definition $\beta_t = \sqrt{2 \log \left(\frac{|\mathcal{X}| \pi^2 t^3}{6\delta} \right)}$, we establish that $\beta_{t,x} \leq \beta_t$. Given that β_t exhibits a monotonic increase with respect to t , we have:

$$\frac{(\text{Reg}_T)^2}{T} \leq \sum_{t=1}^T 4\beta_t^2 \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + 4\beta_T \text{Err}_t \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + \text{Err}_t^2. \tag{12}$$

We now embark on establishing bounds for $\sum_{t=1}^T \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$ and $\sum_{t=1}^T \text{Err}_t \cdot \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$. This endeavor involves invoking Lemma 4 and scrutinizing the maximum information gain, respectively. Simultaneously, we aim to demonstrate that $\sum_{t=1}^T \text{Err}_t^2$ can be bounded by exploiting properties inherent in series.

The first term can be bounded as:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{t=1}^T \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \leq \sum_{t=1}^T \sigma^2(\sigma^{-2} \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)) \\
& \leq \sum_{t=1}^T \sigma^2 \frac{\sigma^{-2}}{\log(1 + \sigma^{-2})} \log(1 + \sigma^{-2} \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)) \\
& \leq \frac{1}{\log(1 + \sigma^{-2})} \sum_{t=1}^T \log(1 + \sigma^{-2} \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)).
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

The first-to-second inequality results from $\frac{s}{\log(1+s)} \leq \frac{\sigma^{-2}}{\log(1+\sigma^{-2})}$ for $s \in [0, \sigma^{-2}]$. Furthermore, in our setting, the maximum information gain can be bounded by $\gamma_T = \mathcal{O}((T \log T)^{\frac{d}{1+d}})$ [2, 4], that is

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \leq \frac{2\gamma_T}{\log(1 + \sigma^{-2})}. \tag{14}$$

Given the assumption that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \text{Err}_t \cdot t^\alpha = C$ and $\alpha > 1$, we have:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\text{Err}_t}{\frac{1}{t^\alpha}} = C, \tag{15}$$

implying the convergence of $\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \text{Err}_t$ due to the comparison test, as $\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{t^\alpha} \leq 1 + \int_1^{\infty} 1/t^\alpha dt = \frac{\alpha}{\alpha-1}$. Without loss of generality, we consider $\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \text{Err}_t = C_1$. By the properties of convergent sequences, the sequence $\{\text{Err}_t\}$ is bounded, expressed as $\text{Err}_t \leq C_2, \forall t$ for all t . Consequently, we can conclude that:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{t=1}^T \text{Err}_t \cdot \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \\
& \leq \sum_{t: \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{x}_t) < 1} \text{Err}_t \cdot \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + \sum_{t: \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \geq 1} \text{Err}_t \cdot \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \\
& \leq \sum_{t: \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) < 1} \text{Err}_t + \sum_{t: \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \geq 1} \text{Err}_t \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \\
& \leq \sum_{t=1}^T \text{Err}_t + C_2 \sum_{t=1}^T \sigma_{t-1}^2(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t),
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

which implies

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \text{Err}_t \cdot \sigma_{t-1}(\mathbf{e}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) \leq C_1 + \frac{2C_2\gamma_T}{\log(1 + \sigma^{-2})}. \tag{17}$$

Simultaneously, we observe: $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\text{Err}_t^2}{t^{2\alpha}} = C^2$, indicating that $\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \text{Err}_t^2$ converges, denoted as $\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \text{Err}_t^2 = C_3$. Consequently, by consolidating the inequalities (12), (14), and (17), we derive:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\text{Reg}_T)^2 \tag{18} \\ & \leq \frac{8}{\log(1 + \sigma^{-2})} \beta_T^2 \gamma_T T + 4\beta_T \left[C_1 + \frac{2C_2 \gamma_T}{\log(1 + \sigma^{-2})} \right] \cdot T + C_3 \cdot T. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, by choosing $\gamma_T = \mathcal{O}((T \log T)^{\frac{d}{1+d}})$ and $\beta_T^2 = 2 \log \left(\frac{|\mathcal{X}| \pi^2 T^3}{6\delta} \right)$, we have:

$$\Pr \left\{ \text{Reg}_T \leq \mathcal{O} \left(\sqrt{\log (|\mathcal{X}|^{\frac{1}{3}} \pi^{\frac{2}{3}} T / \delta^{\frac{1}{3}})} \cdot \gamma_T \cdot T \right) \right\} \geq 1 - \delta. \tag{19}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

2 XGBoost Regression Error

Fig. 1: XGBoost regression error fitted using a power law function of different α .

When illustrating the swift convergence of AI-Lite from a theoretical standpoint, we assume that the prediction error caused by the XGBoost Regression model vanishes at a rate of $1/t^\alpha$. To validate this assumption, we selected data from five physical experiments, specifically extracting the error data generated by the XGBoost Regression model over the first 125 decisions in each experiment and computing the average. As depicted in Fig. 1, the assumption in Eq. (2) that $\alpha > 1$ is valid in a general context, as the regression error can be effectively fitted using a power law function.

References

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